

Effect of Oral motor stimulation on early transition from tube to oral feeding in preterm infants

Samina Naz

Master of Science in Nursing, The University of Lahore, Lahore School of Nursing, Pakistan

Muhammad Afzal

Director Academics, The University of Lahore, Lahore School of Nursing, Pakistan

Madiha Mukhtar

Master of Science in Nursing, The University of Lahore, Lahore School of Nursing Pakistan

ABSTRACT: Background: The development of efficient and safe feeding techniques is one of the most difficult developmental milestones for preterm newborns. Initiation of oral feeding usually takes several days to weeks. Oral motor stimulation enhances feeding skills and leads to early initiation of exclusive oral feed. Objective: To determine the effect of oral stimulation on preterm infants early initiation to oral feeding. Material & Method: Quasi quasi-experimental two-group study was conducted in Children's Hospital Lahore from July to November 2023. Intervention and control group data from 86 preterm infants through purposive sampling was collected through the Early feeding skills assessment tool. The study group received oral stimulation until they achieved the required scores for initiation of oral feed. Results: The preterm mean transition time to oral in the study group who received the intervention was 33 ± 0.43 weeks compared to control group 35 ± 0.7 weeks with ($p < 0.001$) statistically significant difference. Conclusion: The preterm infants who received oral stimulation showed early transition to oral feeding, so we conclude that oral motor stimulation was effective for early switching of preterm infants from tube to oral feeding.

Keywords: Preterm infants, Oral motor stimulation, Initiation, Oral feeding

[Introduction](#)

[Material and methods](#)

[Results](#)

[Discussion](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[Recommendations](#)

[Declarations](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

The most critical time for the survival of a preterm infant is during the newborn period [1]. The number of premature births each year is expected to be over 15 million [2]. Worldwide, almost 15 million premature infants are born annually and this rate is increasing [3].

In low-middle-income countries, the prevalence of premature birth is approximately 92% and 99% of these premature infants die every year. [4] approximately 40 to 70 % of preterm infants experience feeding difficulties [5]. Lack of neurological, cardio-respiratory, oral motor readiness [4], gastrointestinal maturity, and coordination of sucking, swallowing, and breath, which is required for oral feeding at birth absent in preterm infants [6]

Premature infants frequently have feeding disorders at birth and may require a period of non-oral feeding until the infants [7], safely progress to full oral feeding so that they can be discharged from the hospital [8]. Due to a lack of rules and the diversity of assessment practices, the normal transition from non-oral to oral feeding is unclear.[9] Moreover, Long-term IV feeding raises the possibility of developing late-onset sepsis requiring a longer hospital stay and costing more to treat [10].

Delaying enteral feeding can also lead to gastrointestinal mucosal degeneration and an increase in the risk of necrotizing enterocolitis[11].

Traditional" feeding regimens decide whether to start or delay oral feeding based on factors like the infant's weight, gestational age, and health [12]. The baby might be compromised by these requirements, and parents and caregivers might feel more anxious and frustrated [13].

The gold standard for discharging a premature newborn from the NICU is oral nourishment [14]. Early oral feeding experience promotes maturity and increases oral feeding success [15].

Several characteristics determines whether the premature infant is ready for oral feeding trails or not [16]. These characteristics of oral feeding readiness are Physiological stability including Heart rate, oxygen saturation, temperature, respiratory rate and skin colour [17,18], Neuro-behavioural maturity including maintaining flexed body posture, being awake and alert [19], [20], crying for feed and demonstrating the suck- swallow breathing coordination [21]. One of the most important element to assess the infant readiness for oral feeding trails is the trophic feeding tolerance and age of infant that is calculated by mothers last menstrual period [22].

Monitoring the heart and respiratory rates continuously throughout feeding allows for the evaluation of the neonatal cardiorespiratory response to feeding. The following factors can help the midwife foresee neonatal discomfort: A shift in the tone of relaxed muscles, a change in colour, rolling of the eyes, a cough, and an impression of drowning Feeding should cease if any of these symptoms appear so that the baby can regain cardiorespiratory stability [23].

In low middle income countries due to lack of resources only limited number of studies had been conducted related to interventions regarding the early transition from tube to oral feeding in preterm infants. Moreover, in those studies volume driven feeding model was being used for transition to oral feeding. Volume driven feeding model meant if an infant took 150ml milk per oral per day or took eight successful feeds per oral per day infant was able to transit to oral feed. In Pakistan no study has been conducted related to this intervention and this was the first study to examine the effect of oral motor stimulation on early transition from tube to oral feeding in preterm infants by using Early Feeding Skills Assessment tool and through nurses training in public sector Hospital of Lahore Pakistan.

Objective

To determine the effect of oral motor stimulation on early transition from tube to oral feeding in preterm infants

Problem Statement

Premature infants require a period of non-oral feeding until they safely progress to full oral feeding. Whether to start or delay oral feeding depends on factors like infant weight, gestational age, and health in most developing countries. This lead to the delayed initiation of oral feeding and puts the infants at risk of developing Necrotizing Enterocolitis. Naz et al, (2022) study conducted at the Neonatal Nursery Unit (NNU) of The Children's Hospital Lahore Pakistan that depicted the preterm infants' mean exclusive oral feeding initiation time was 35 to 36 weeks. However, A Morag et al., (2019) study conducted at the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit of the University of Ottawa Canada showed normally Preterm infants'

suck-swallow breathing coordination develops at age of 32 to 34 weeks and they can take oral feed at this age.

Significance

Oral motor stimulation is an evidence-based intervention to raise neonatal care standards and maintain the best long-term outcomes for the care of preterm neonates. Unfortunately, our NICU regulations were not following this oral motor stimulation approach. This study improved the feeding skills of preterm infants because Oral motor stimulation improved the preterm infant's feeding outcomes and promoted the emergence of unassisted oral feeding/early switching to oral feeding.

2. Material and methods

Study Design: Two groups Quasi-Experimental research design was used to accomplish this study.

Study Tool: Early Feeding Skills Assessment

The tool Early Feeding Skill Assessment was originally developed by [16]

It has 4 domains.

1. Domain1: Ability To Maintain Engagement in feeding: This domain has 3 items score range of 3-9
2. Domain 2: Ability to Organize Oral-Motor Functioning: This domain has 7 items score range of 7-21
3. Domain 3: Ability to Coordinate Swallowing: This domain has 6 items score range of 6-18
4. Domain 4: Ability to maintain Physiologic Stability: This domain has 12 items scores ranging from 12 to 36

Scoring Criteria:

Preterm newborns are scored according to their readiness for oral feeding: unable receives one point, some able receives two points, and able receives three points. There are 28 different items recorded for every neonate. The total oral feeding readiness score for the preterm neonates is 84.

1. High ability score, The preterm infants will be successfully transit to oral feeding score >70 or >85%
2. Intermediate ability score, The preterm infants will be included in the study intervention score range between 55 to 70 or 66% to 85%
3. Low ability score, The preterm infants will not be included in study intervention due to complications or admission in intensive care unit <66% or score <55

Setting: The study will be conducted at the Neonatal Nursery Unit of The Children's Hospital Lahore.

Study Population: Preterm infants admitted to the Neonatal Nursery Unit at Children's Hospital Lahore.

Sample Size: The Sample size was calculated with a 95% confidence level, $d=0.09$, 43 infants in each group and the expected mean score of oral feeding initiation time was $28.2+ 0.3$ days [17].

Sampling Technique: A Purposive (criterion) sampling technique was used for inclusion of study participants.

Please select the desired unknown:		Please enter the remaining values:	
☐ Confidence level (%)		$1 - \alpha$	95
☐ Absolute precision required		d	0.09
☐ Relative precision		s	0.00445544554
☐ Population mean		μ	20.2
☐ Population standard deviation		σ	0.3
☐ Population variance		σ^2	0.09
☒ Sample size		n	43
$n = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 \sigma^2}{d^2} \text{ or } \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 \sigma^2}{s^2 \mu^2}$		<input type="button" value="Print"/>	
		<input type="button" value="Help"/>	
		<input type="button" value="Close"/>	

Inclusion criteria:

1. 29 to 32 gestational weeks of infants.
2. Preterm infants on tube feeding with weak sucking and swallowing ability.
3. Hemodynamic and physiologically stable preterm infants
4. Intermediate ability score, score range 55 to 70 or 66% to 84%.

Exclusion criteria:

- a. Preterm infants suffering from congenital anomalies
- b. Critically ill and those on mechanical ventilators
- c. Low ability score, <66% or score <55.

Data Collection Process

The process of collecting data was started after the approval of the Research Ethics Committee (REC). Before the data collection written informed consent was taken from the mother of all infants.

Pre-intervention phase: The researcher used the Early Feeding Skills Assessment Scale for the inclusion of study participants on the first day of the session. Preterm newborns who were eligible and met the inclusion requirements were assigned to the study group and the control group. Infants in the study group received intervention (oral stimulation) whereas the infants in the control group received regular care alone. Oral stimulation is a stimulation technique used to speed up the tube feeding initiation time.

Intervention: The intervention group received an oral stimulation, as suggested by [18] that was carried out by wearing gloves after the preterm neonate had their diaper changed and became aware and quiet. According to the newborn babies' clinical stability, the trial intervention began 15 to 30 minutes prior to tube feeding. The first 3 minutes of stimulation, was done by gently stretching the cheeks in a C pattern, lip roll, lip curl or lip stretch, gum massage, tongue and palate massage, and gentle stroke of the palate. For the final two minutes of stimulation, non-nutritive sucking was used. Pre-feeding oral stimulation and NNS were used twice daily.

Evaluation phase: Preterm infants' feeding skills were assessed through the EFSA at 32 weeks. The infants who achieved a >70 score >85% were successfully shifted to oral feeding. The infants who did not achieve the required score were re-stimulated until they got the required scores. Meanwhile, the researcher assessed the oral feeding time of preterm infants' in the control group with the same tool. To ascertain the impact of oral stimulation on preterm newborns' feeding progression and time to sniff away the feeding tube, the study group and control group were compared at the end of study.

Data Analysis Procedure

Data was analyzed through the SPSS version 22.0. Descriptive statistics were analyzed through percentage (%) and frequency distribution. Inferential statistics: This data analysis involved the utilization of the Friedman test due to the abnormal distribution of the

data. Kolmogorov Smirnov was used because the preterm infants' Sample size was more than 50. The Friedman test was applied to compare the mean scores of pre and post-intervention in both control and study groups. P Value for both tests $p < 0.05$ was statistical significant.

3. Results

Table: 1 Demographic characteristic of Preterm Infants on Tube feeding

Gender	Demographic Variables	Control Group	Interventional Group
		n %	n %
Male			
20(46.51)			
20(46.51)			
Female		23(53.49)	23(53.49)
Age	29 Weeks	13(30.2)	5(11.6)
	30 Weeks	13(30.2)	26(60.5)
	31 Weeks	04(9.3)	01(2.3)
	32 Weeks	13(30.2)	11(25.6)

Descriptive Statistics analyzed by frequency 'n' and percentage '%'

Demographic Characteristics: The table showed the demographic characteristics of preterm infants on tube feeding in both the control group and the study group. Results revealed that the majority of infants were female with tube feeding in both groups control group (53.49, 23) and in the study group (53.49, 23). In age groups, infants were greater in number in the age of 30 ($f=26$, 60.5%) in the study group as compared to (30.2%, 13) in the control group.

Table: 2 Preterm infants Oral Feeding time

EFSA at	Variable	Control Group	Study Group
Baseline		Mean $\pm$ (SD)	Mean $\pm$ (SD)
39.47 $\pm$ 2.844			
38.38 $\pm$ 4.844			
EFSA at 32 th Week		63.13 $\pm$ 2.968	50.92 $\pm$ 5.397
EFSA at 33 th Week		79.96 $\pm$ 3.142	59.67 $\pm$ 3.485
EFSA at 34 th Week	-		67.75 $\pm$ 2.308
EFSA at 35 th Week	-		80.71 $\pm$ 3.839

Friedman test, Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) $P < 0.05$

Transition time: The Friedman test, a non-parametric test, was applied for the variable of early feeding skills assessment to compare outcome variables throughout the oral feeding initiation time duration. P-value < 0.05 was taken as significant. According to the results, p-value was less than 0.05 for both groups which showed significant improvement in both groups. In control group there was a significant improvement from baseline (38.38+ 4.844) to 35 weeks (80.71+ 3.839) while in the experimental group the results were also significant from baseline (39.47 $\pm$ 2.844) to last 33 weeks (23.9545 $\pm$ 1.7314). These results show significant improvement between groups as more improvement was seen in the experimental group ($p < 0.05$). The control group initiation time was 35 weeks while the experimental group initiation time was 33 weeks.

Table: 3 Comparison of Oral Feeding initiation time in both Control and intervention Group

Transition time	Variable	Group		P value
		Control Group Mean±(SD)	Study Group Mean±(SD)	
35 weeks±0.7				
33 weeks±0.43				0.00

Friedman test, Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) P <0.05

Transition time: Table#4 shows the comparison of oral feeding initiation time in both Control and Intervention groups. The mean oral feeding initiation time in the control group was 35 weeks±3.23 who did not receive the oral motor stimulation. Whereas, the mean oral feeding initiation time in study group who received oral motor stimulation was 33 weeks±0.43 (P-value < 0.001) which was lesser than the control group, hence it is proved that there is a significant difference in transition time of study group who received the intervention (p-value <0.05)

4. Discussion

Successful independent oral feeding is one of fundamental milestones in the growth and development of preterm. Preterm infants in neonatal intensive care units usually suffer from delayed initiation of oral feeding which leads to developmental issues later in life [19]. Oral motor stimulation exercise is used to facilitate the newborns' oral feeding abilities and early initiation of oral feeding. Oral motor stimulation exercises stimulate the sensory and motor structure of the oral cavity including lips, gums, cheeks, tongue, and palate [20].

Oral motor stimulation intervention is widely used in various research studies to facilitate the early improvement of oral motor abilities, to improve the muscle tone of the oral cavity and its movement along with the maturation of suck swallow breathing coordination [21].

Regarding preterm infants' gestational age is noticed that the highest mean age of the study group infants was 33 + 0.43 weeks and the mean age of the control group who did not receive the oral motor stimulation was 35weeks +0.7, these study findings were similar to the study [22], according to study result finding the highest mean age of the not received group was (35.1+0.7 weeks).

The current study findings demonstrate that mostly the preterm infants who received oral stimulation exercise had higher early feeding skills score than the control group who had moderate early feeding skills score when compared at 32 weeks, 33 weeks, 34 weeks, and 35 weeks. According to the researcher, it may be due to the effect of study intervention which led to the improvement of oral motor abilities in preterm infants while the control group did not receive oral motor stimulation and had moderate ability scores. These study findings following the study [23] study group had a lower transition time (25 days) to unassisted oral feeding in comparison to the control group (35 days). However, these study findings were in opposition to the study [24] that showed a majority of study participants had mild to moderate differences in switching time to unassisted oral feeding at the end of the study.

The relationship between the total scores of early feeding skills assessment of the study group infants with their demographic characteristics, a statistically positive correlation was found between gestational weeks of study group with maintenance of engagement in feeding, organization of oral motor functioning, coordination in swallowing, and

physiological stability. According to the researcher, it was because that with the increase of age preterm infants' early feeding skills improved. These study findings are in line of a study [15] that found a significant correlation between gestational age and feeding skills. While in contrast to the study [25] which found no significant correlation between total feeding skills scores and infants' gestational age of the control group. Study [26] found no statistically significant correlation between infants feeding skills scores in the control group and demo-graphical data.

5. Conclusion

According to the study results the preterm infants who received the OMS intervention were early transitioned to oral feed as compared to the control group infants who did not receive the intervention, so we conclude that oral motor stimulation was effective for early switching of preterm infants from tube to oral feeding.

6. Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested based on the present study:

- More advanced studies should be planned to investigate the effect of oral stimulation intervention with a large sample size as it is the safe and effective technique that has an everlasting and greater impact on care of preterm infants.
- Furthermore OMS should be incorporated in NNU for caring for preterm infants as it is effective and safe intervention.

7. Declarations

Consents to participants

Informed consent was taken from all the mothers of preterm infants

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgment

I would like to extend my heartfelt appreciation to my supervisor, Muhammad Afzal, for his constant inspiration, sincerity, and cooperation throughout the entire course.

Limitations

The current study was limited to preterm infants with tube feeding and no comorbidities, our findings cannot be generalized to other populations.

Abbreviations

OS: Oral stimulation. EFSA: Early feeding skills assessment.. NNU: Non-nutritive sucking

References

1. Li, L., et al., Clinical effects of oral motor intervention combined with non-nutritive sucking on oral feeding in preterm infants with dysphagia. *Jornal de Pediatria*, 2022. 98: p. 635-640.
2. Muñoz Jordán, D.V. and B.I. Zambrano Tacuri, La novela experimental de Jorge Dávila Vázquez en el desarrollo de las competencias lectoras. 2021, Universidad de Guayaquil. Facultad de Filosofía, Letras y Ciencias de la
3. Fox, H. and E. Callander, Cost of preterm birth to Australian mothers: Assessing the financial impact of a birth outcome with an increasing prevalence. *Journal of Paediatrics and Child Health*, 2021. 57(5): p. 618-625.
4. Mustapha, B., et al., Prevalence and associated morbidities of preterm neonatal admissions at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, North-Eastern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Paediatrics*, 2020. 47(3): p. 264–269-264–269.
5. Zimmerman, E. and A. Rosner, Feeding swallowing difficulties in the first three years of life: a preterm and full-term infant comparison. *Journal of Neonatal Nursing*, 2018. 24(6): p. 331-335.
6. Chawanpaiboon, S., et al., Global, regional, and national estimates of levels of preterm birth in 2014: a systematic review and modelling analysis. *The Lancet global health*, 2019. 7(1): p. e37-e46.
7. Hanif, A., et al., Prevalence and risk factors of preterm birth in Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc*, 2020. 70(4): p. 577-582.
8. Chun, R. and M.L. Skinner, The Upper Airway and Swallowing. *Pediatric Swallowing and Feeding: Assessment and Management*, 2019: p. 149.
9. Abo El Magd Fathi, F., W. Elsayed Ouda, and M. Ali Kunswa, Nurses' Practices for Sensorimotor Stimulation to Enhance Oral Feeding of preterm Infants: An Assessment Study. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*, 2022. 13(3): p. 314-323.
10. Gulati, I.K., Z. Sultana, and S.R. Jadcherla, Approach to Feeding Difficulties in Neonates and Infants: A Comprehensive Overview. *Clinics in Perinatology*, 2020. 47(2): p. 265-276.
11. Muelbert, M., J.E. Harding, and F.H. Bloomfield. Nutritional policies for late preterm and early term infants—can we do better? in *Seminars in Fetal and Neonatal Medicine*. 2019. Elsevier.
12. Mayerl, C.J., et al., Preterm birth disrupts the development of feeding and breathing coordination. *Journal of Applied Physiology*, 2019. 126(6): p. 1681-1686.
13. Marandola, J. and K. Lasby, 8 How Do You Wean to Suck Feed? Late Preterm Infants: A Guide for Nurses, Midwives, Clinicians and Allied Health Professionals, 2019: p. 99.
14. Louyeh, Z.S., et al., Comparing the effect of breast milk odor and incubator cover on nutritional adequacy of premature infants: a quasi-experimental study. *Medical-Surgical Nursing Journal*, 2020. 9(2).
15. Chang, Y.-J., et al., Preterm oral feeding scale to assist in deciding initial oral feeding of preterm infants in neonatal intensive care units. *Pediatrics & Neonatology*, 2022. 63(3): p. 269-275.
16. Thoyre, S., C. Shaker, and K. Pridham, The early feeding skills assessment for preterm infants. *Neonatal Network*, 2005. 24(3): p. 7-16.
17. Mohamed Ibrahim Nassar, H., A. Awad Helmy, and M. Mohamed Ahmed Ayed, Effect of oral stimulation technique application on promoting feeding among preterm infants. *Egyptian Journal of Nursing and Health Sciences*, 2021. 2(2): p. 298-316.
18. Lessen, B.S., Effect of the premature infant oral motor intervention on feeding progression and length of stay in preterm infants. *Advances in Neonatal care*, 2011. 11(2): p. 129-139.
19. Mohamed Arafa, N., R. Ibrahim Mostafa Radwan, and A.E.-R.A. Mohammed, Effect of olfactory and gustatory stimulations on preterm neonates' feeding progression and sniffing away feeding tube. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*, 2021. 12(4): p. 1681-1699.

20. Girgin, B.A. and D. Gözen, Turkish neonatal nurses' knowledge and practices regarding the transition to oral feeding in preterm infants: A descriptive, cross-sectional study. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 2020. 53: p. e179-e185.
21. Pighetti, D., J. Hirschwald, and O. Gilheaney, Developmental feeding milestones in the transition from non-oral feeding to oral feeding in premature infants: a scoping review. *Speech, Language and Hearing*, 2022. 25(1): p. 82-97.
22. Li, L., et al., Clinical effects of oral motor intervention combined with non-nutritive sucking on oral feeding in preterm infants with dysphagia. *Jornal de Pediatria*, 2022.
23. Chen, D., et al., Effect of oral motor intervention on oral feeding in preterm infants: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *American journal of speech-language pathology*, 2021. 30(5): p. 2318-2328.
24. Griffith, T., et al., A behavioral epigenetics model to predict oral feeding skills in preterm infants. *Advances in Neonatal Care*, 2020. 20(5): p. 392-400.
25. Liu, Y., et al., Early combined rehabilitation intervention to improve the short-term prognosis of premature infants. *BMC pediatrics*, 2021. 21(1): p. 1-7.
26. Morag, I., et al., Transition from nasogastric tube to oral feeding: the role of parental guided responsive feeding. *Frontiers in pediatrics*, 2019. 7: p. 190.